

European Agroforestry Federation

CAP Simplification Proposal from the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF) to DG AGRI. Submitted 3/4/25

An agroforestry carbon farming starter pack - to simplify and link existing agricultural tree-planting interventions

Introduction

Agroforestry interventions in the previous CAP (2014-2022) were not successful, for a range of reasons including bureaucratic burden and fears over the loss of basic payments. Final details are awaited, but of the initially planned 85 Mha, only around 5 Mha had been established by the end of 2023 (DG AGRI Pers Comm).

In the present CAP (2023-2027) it is impossible to estimate planting targets, since: a) Member States have not distinguished “afforestation” rates from “agroforestation” in Result Indicator 17, and b) an increasing number of MS are funding all of their forestry expenditure outside the CAP and not reporting with CAP metrics (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #19](#)). Moreover, it is difficult to estimate the current area of agroforestry and trees outside the forest at EU level¹ due to inadequate farm-scale metrics and insufficient data sharing (see [EURAF Policy Briefing #70](#)). This has major implications for the CAP and related legislation like the Nature Restoration Regulation, Carbon Removals Certification Framework and the Forest Monitoring Regulation.

EURAF’s simplification proposal therefore focuses on (i) simplifying existing tree planting measures in a simple “starter pack” (ii) making better use of existing data at farm scale, (iii) strengthening synergies with related policies like the NRR and CRCF.

Data in the [Catalogue of CAP Interventions](#) shows that only 9 countries have planned expenditure on agroforestry (BE-F, CZ, DE, EL, ES, IT, PL, PT, SK). Support rates are generally low (except CZ), and may only be available in some regions (ES, IT). Support may be offered only for management, without contributing to the planting costs (BE-F), or only be available to mature trees without aiding establishment (DE, EL). There is therefore a need for support to be simplified and to ensure that the four stages of **planning, establishment, initial maintenance and longer-term support** are included. CAP maintenance support is limited to 5-years, and this is one reason for the trend of Member States (now France and most of Germany) to take their forestry spend outside the CAP, through the Agricultural Block Exemption Regulation ([2022/2472](#)). Carbon-certification could fill this gap, simplify CAP funding rules, and persuade larger numbers of farmers to take up agroforestry carbon farming (AFCF). **Fortunately**, the initial draft of the CRFC Carbon Farming Delegated Act (DG CLIMA [Nov 2024](#)) suggests that trees supported by CAP funding will not be considered ineligible due to the CRCF “financial additionality” test, provided they have been established for no longer than five years.

¹ The most used estimation was provided by den [Herder et al 2017](#) suggesting that 8.8% of the EU agricultural land area is agroforestry. This figure is an approximation, however, given the sampling method (LUCAS) and assumptions made.

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Table 1: Measures in Member States which specifically refer to agroforestry. New measures are being developed in Austria. France and Ireland have measures outside the CAP

MS	Article	Code	O.16 (total)	R.17 (total)	Measure
BE-FL	Art 70	3.7	€281,384		Management of agroforestry systems (boslandbouwsystemen)
CZ	Art 70	26.7	€1,357,200		Caring for an established agroforestry system
CZ	Art 73-74	42.73		€3,917,700	Establishment of an agroforestry system
DE	Art 31	DZ-0403 –			Maintaining agroforestry management on arable land and permanent grassland
EL	Art 31	P1-31.05 –		€66,564,568	Improvement of agroforestry ecosystems, rich in landscape elements
ES	Art 70	6502.2	€27,069,248		Maintenance of Forests and Agroforests
ES	Art 73-74	6881.1		€68,809,809	Non productive investments in afforestation and agroforestry systems
IT	Art 70	SRA28	€66,080,718		Support for maintenance of forestation/afforestation and agroforestry systems
IT	Art 73/74	SRD05		€47,387,981	Forestation/afforestation and agroforestry systems on agricultural land
PL	Art 70	I.8.8			Afforestation and afforestation premiums and agroforestry schemes
PL	Art 73-74	I 10.13.		€5,998,785	Establishment of agroforestry systems
PT	Art 70	C.1.1.3			Agroforestry Mosaic (Attributed to O.14 and R.14, R31, R.33)
PT	Art 70	D.2.2			Management of the montado (agroforestry) by Results
PT	Art 73-74	C.3.2.2		€3,360,000	Setting up agroforestry systems
PT	Art 73-74	F.2.2		€300,000	Investment in the creation and regeneration of agroforestry systems
SK	Art 70	70.01	€2,932,150	€2,932,150	Protection and maintenance of trees within the established Agroforestry system
SK	Art 73-74	73.01		€2,932,150	Establishing an agroforestry system

Proposal

EURAF's [Policy Briefing #8](#) suggests that MS should create an **integrated carbon farming starter-pack** including:

1. **Ecoscheme** (Article 31) support for baseline soil sampling and pre-planting advice in year 0
2. **Investment Measure** (Article 74) support in year 1 for tree-planting and protection
3. **Agri Environment Climate Measure** (Article 70) support in years 2-5 for initial maintenance
4. **Carbon Farming Certification** from year 6 onwards, with monitoring every 5 years until the agreed end of the rotation (the carbon certification “activity period”).

Most Member States would fully adopt Steps 1-3 in their CAP Programmes, others (e.g. IE, NL, FI, FR) would fund the Investment and AECM measures with national funding through the Agricultural Block Exemption Regulation. CAP Interventions to establish woody landscape features would also be integrated into this “**agroforestry carbon farming (AFCF) starter pack**”.

Monitoring

DG CLIMA is committed to creating a geospatial register of carbon farming parcels by 2028. DG AGRI (through EEA and JRC) would ensure that all Member States record the location of the lines and groups of trees established through this “AFCF starter pack” in their CAP GSAA-LIPS systems, and provide open access to this in their INSPIRE Portals². Total areas of agroforestry would be recorded in Result Indicator 17.3 and the area of woody landscape features in R.17.4. Areas of all types of protected landscape features would continue to be recorded in Result Indicator R.34 (noting that this excludes non-productive areas like fallow land). EURAF [Policy Briefing #70](#) gives more detail on simplification and sharing of agricultural, environmental and forestry metrics.

² There are currently 9 countries which do not make GSAA/LPIS information available on open portals: BG, HR, DE, SL, HU, IT, MT, PL, RO. See [Milestone 6](#) Report of the DigitAF Project

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EURAF [Policy Briefing #26](#) gives estimates of the “tree deserts” in Europe and the potential contribution of agroforestry to Europe’s land sector emission targets. EURAF’s mission is for tree cover on agricultural land to exceed 10% by 2040 .. i.e. all the red pixels in Figure 1 should turn green.

Figure 1 EURAF has monitored **Tree-Cover-Density (TCD) on agricultural land in the 39 EEA countries**. Areas of white are non-agricultural areas. Red areas are priority planting zones where TCD is particularly low. Source: Copernicus TCD-2018 superimposed on Corine agricultural land for 2018. Each pixel covers 1 ha (100 m x 100 m). The map was produced for the EU DigitAF project by Planet Inc and the European Forest Institute.

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